

Enhancing User Control in AI-Based Video Summarization for Social Media^{*}

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Abstract. This paper presents an AI-based tool for producing video summaries for sharing on social media, that offers editorial control over the results of the AI analysis. Leveraging SoA models for video summarization and aspect ratio transformation, it provides the users with a set of recommendations about the parts of the video that should be included in the summary. Through an interactive user interface, it enables the users to make the necessary edits, thus assisting the production of video summaries that comply with social media with regard to the video's length and aspect ratio, and fully meet the users' needs.

Keywords: Video summarization · Video aspect ratio transformation · Editorial control · Artificial Intelligence · Social media

1 Introduction

The rise of social media fueled a growing need for short videos that grab the viewer's attention. Content creators often have to trim-down their videos based on the optimal video presentation format of each social media platform (e.g., Facebook reels can be up to 90 sec. long with a 16:9 aspect ratio, while Facebook stories can be 30 sec. long with a 9:16 ratio). Adapting videos to fit these varying requirements can be challenging and time-consuming. Only a couple of tools can facilitate this process [7, 4], by creating video summaries based on different options about the summary duration and aspect ratio. The users' feedback after using the tool from [7], made clear that they appreciate the offered speedup by the automated analysis; though, it highlighted their need to have editorial control over the final results. Motivated by this feedback, in this paper, we introduce an extended version of the video summarization tool from [7], that allows users to refine and adjust the AI-based generated video summaries and aspect ratio transformation results. Through its interactive user interface (UI), our tool facilitates the generation of video summaries that comply with various social media platforms, and fully meet the users' needs in terms of content.

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2 Related Work

A growing number of AI-based video summarization tools are available online. Paid tools, such as [5], [1], and [3] use AI to segment the video into clips and score a small subset of these clips based on estimates about their virality. These tools typically provide a set of video segments likely to capture viewers' attention, rather than creating a cohesive summary of the most important parts of the full-length video. Other tools, such as [7], [4], and [2], support the creation of video summaries according to various presentation format requirements. [7] allows the creation of summaries according to the recommended duration and aspect ratio of different social media platforms, while it enables the use of fully-customized values for these features. [4] supports only YouTube videos, and offers limited options about the duration (short, medium, long) and the aspect ratio (9:16, 1:1, 16:9) of the summary. Finally, [2] permits the creation of summaries up to 30 sec. long, but does not support aspect ratio transformation. The proposed solution is most closely related to [7, 4]. Nevertheless, contrary to these tools, our solution supports editorial control over the analysis results, thus allowing the generation of video summaries that fully meet the users' expectations.

3 Proposed Solution

The proposed solution (available at <https://idt.iti.gr/summary-editor>) is an extension of the web-based tool for video summarization, presented in [7]. It consists of a front-end user interface (UI) and a back-end component that communicate via REST calls. The former allows interaction with the user, and the latter integrates AI-based technologies for video **segmentation**, **summarization** and **aspect ratio transformation**, and produces the video summary. Our solution extends [7] by: i) offering to the user editorial control over the results of the AI-based video summarization and aspect ratio transformation, and ii) integrating an advanced AI-based method for video summarization.

3.1 Front-end UI

The UI of the proposed solution (shown in Fig. 1) allows users to submit an online or locally-stored video for summarization after selecting the desired duration and aspect ratio. Users can choose from predefined presets for various social media platforms, or fully customize their selection. Once the analysis initiates, its progress can be monitored; upon completion, the results of the automated video segmentation and summarization are provided to the user for check.

During the next step, the user can review the video summarization results and make any necessary adjustments, through the interface shown in Fig. 2. This interface includes: (1) a video player showing the current playback time and total video duration on the left side, and the selected summary duration and target duration on the right side; (2) buttons to play/pause the video, navigate frame-by-frame, and navigate fragment-by-fragment; (3) a radio button to

Interactive Video Summarizer

This service lets you submit videos (up to 20 minutes long) in various formats and generate summaries for use in various social media channels.

[Insert a video URL \(for supported video platforms, please click Usage instructions\)](#)

OR

Drag & Drop
or Upload local video
(mp4, webm, mov, wmv, ogv, mkv, avi)

OPTIONAL: Enter your email to get a 24-hours-active link to the summarization results

I want to generate a summary for posting it on:

Twitter Facebook (feed) Facebook (stories) Instagram (feed) Instagram (stories) YouTube TikTok Custom

Summary characteristics:

Video length up to seconds

Aspect ratio

Fig. 1. The landing page of the UI.

switch between the original video and the formed summary based on the selected fragments (offering a preview of it); (4) a radio button to specify whether the audio should be also included in the summary; (5) an interactive time-bar showing the video fragments and indicating the suggested/selected ones for inclusion in the summary (dark-coloured ones), that can be removed by double-clicking on them; (6) an additional time-bar that allows the user to zoom in on specific parts of the video for more accurate editing; (7) a representative keyframe for any video fragment, shown after hovering over a fragment in the time-bar; (8) an arrow-slider that provides easy navigation through the video and allows the definition of new fragments by specifying their start and end time. After completing the required edits, the user can proceed to the next step of the process by clicking on the designated button.

In the next step, the user can review the spatially demarcated regions of the frames within the summary based on the selected aspect ratio, via the interface shown in Fig. 3. This interface includes: (1) a video player displaying the summary, current playback time, and total duration; (2) the frames' regions suggested for cropping; (3) buttons for playing/pausing the video, navigating frame-by-frame, moving by 10 frames, and navigating fragment-by-fragment; (4) a collapsible section for uploading an audio file or an SRT file for subtitle inclusion; (5) an interactive time-bar showing the video fragments; and (6) an arrow-slider for video navigation. The red line on the time-bar indicates where smart cropping has been applied. Users can adjust the bounding box position across a sequence of frames by modifying its position in the first and last frames

Fig. 2. The interface for editing the summarization results

Fig. 3. The interface for editing the smart cropping results.

of the sequence. The edited sequence will turn the corresponding part of the red line green, showing that the bounding box has been adjusted via interpolation. While playing the video, the bounding boxes in the edited frames appear in green at the user-selected positions. Users can revert adjustments by double-clicking the green part of the time-bar, which deletes the edits and restores the original data, turning the line back to red. Once edits are complete, the user can generate the video summary by clicking the designated button. After processing, the original video and the summary are displayed through an interactive page with two video players (Fig. 4), and the user can download the final video summary from this page.

Fig. 4. The video players of the page showing the analysis results.

3.2 Back-end component

The submitted video is fragmented into shots using a pre-trained model of the method from [16], that shows SoA performance on various benchmarking datasets (e.g., ClipShots [17], BBC [12] and RAI [13]). Then, **video summarization** is performed using a pre-trained model of PGL-SUM [8] on the TVSum dataset [15]. PGL-SUM is a SoA video summarization method that employs global and local multi-head attention mechanisms with positional encoding, to model the frames' position and dependence at different levels of granularity. The output of PGL-SUM is a series of frame-level importance scores, that are used (averaged) to compute fragment-level importance. The fragments are then ranked in descending order and the top-K of them are selected for inclusion in the summary (k relates to the summary duration). Fragments shorter than two seconds are excluded, while the selected fragments that exceed six seconds, are trimmed by selecting the most important subset of frames, to promote higher informativeness and diversity in the video summary. For **video aspect ratio transformation**, we employ the method of [7], which extends the one in [11] by using a SoA approach for saliency prediction [14], and shows advanced performance on the RetargetVid dataset [10].

4 Experimental results

To evaluate the proposed solution, we conducted a study including 10 participants and five videos from the TVSum dataset [15], with a 16:9 aspect ratio and 4.7 min. average duration. The participants were asked to create two different video summaries for each video, with a 4:5 aspect ratio and a duration equal to 30 and 120 sec., respectively.

To assess the effectiveness of the AI-based methods for video summarization and aspect ratio transformation, we computed the average overlap between the analysis results and the humans' preferences. For video summarization, we quantified this overlap using F-Score, following [6]. For aspect ratio transformation,

Table 1. The average overlap between the suggestions made by the proposed solution and the human preferences, in each processing step.

Summary duration	Video Summarization (F-Score %)	Video Aspect Ratio Transformation (IoU)
120 sec.	85.4	0.967
30 sec.	64.7	0.933

Table 2. The average time needed for the automatic analysis and the editorial control of the analysis results in each processing step.

Summary duration	Video Summarization		Video Aspect Ratio Transformation	
	Automatic analysis (min.)	Editing time (min.)	Automatic analysis (min.)	Editing time (min.)
120 sec.	1.19	4.26	0.34	2.13
30 sec.	1.19	2.48	0.21	1.10

we measured this overlap by computing the Intersection over Union (IoU), similarly to [11, 7]. The results in Table 1, show that there is a noticeable overlap between the AI-suggested and the human-edited summaries ($> 85\%$) when producing a summary of 120 sec. long. In the case of 30 sec. summaries, this overlap is reduced, as expected, since it is more challenging to achieve a strong agreement between AI and humans for very short summaries. The results for aspect ratio transformation, highlight the effectiveness of the integrated method. The selected regions by this method are highly aligned with the humans' selections in both summarization scenarios, as indicated by the very high (> 0.93) IoU scores. The aforementioned findings show that the automated analysis results are well-aligned to the users' needs and require a small amount of editing effort.

To evaluate the time efficiency of the proposed solution, we measured the average time needed for the automatic analysis and the editorial control over the analysis results, in each processing step. The results in Table 2 indicate that it takes only a few minutes for a user to create a summary that is tailored to his/her needs using the proposed solution. We anticipate that the editing time can be significantly reduced by integrating explainable AI components (e.g., [9]), which can help to build a level of trust between users and our solution; this will be studied in future work.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we presented an interactive AI-based tool that facilitates the creation of customized video summaries for various social media platforms. By integrating advanced AI models in a highly interactive user interface, our tool allows users to refine and customize both the video summarization and the aspect ratio transformation recommendations. Our solution puts emphasis on editorial control, helping creators to produce video content that meets various social media platform requirements, as well as their personal preferences.

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